

Pelargonium fergusoniae

Malva

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© A. Senekal

Group: Eudicot

Size: 10 -20 cm in height.

Distribution:

Native to the Western Cape, this plant's range spans from the Hex River Valley to Riversdale.

Importance:

This species represents a major taxonomic group within *Pelargonium*, a highly diverse genus with economic, research and conservation value. As an endangered species its assembled genome will support studies of population genetic patterns and inform future conservation strategies.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 37.11 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.87 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.77 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 96.7% [Single: 78.2%, Duplicated: 18.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 52 766.52 kilobases

Contig number: 734

Sample Contributor contact details:

Annerie Senekal

Stellenbosch University Botanical Garden

amsenekal@sun.ac.za

DIPL**MICS**
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published: 2026-05-08

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21026257>

